

the mixed chelate containing cysteine and biguanide ended in failure.

Experimental

Biguanide acid sulphate¹ and *cis*-diammine *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) base² were prepared by published procedures. Aminoacidato *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) compounds³ were also obtained by procedures developed in this laboratory (α -alanH = alanine; valinH = valine; leucH = leucine).

dl-Methioninato *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) iodide :

Cis-diammine *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) base (0.003 mol) in water (20 ml) was allowed to react with *dl*-methionine (0.003 mol) on a steam bath for forty minutes. After ammonia evolution had ceased the solution was filtered and neutralised with HCl (1 : 3) followed by the addition of KI (~1 gm). The solution was then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The separated red-violet crystals were further purified from hot water. (Found : Co, 8.8; N, 22.8; I, 37.1; H₂O, 2.7%. Calc. for [Co(*dl*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂·I₂·H₂O : Co, 8.7; N, 22.6; I, 37.3; H₂O, 2.6%).

dl-Methioninato *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) sulphate :

The above reaction mixture was neutralised with 10% H₂SO₄. The solution was concentrated to 10 ml and on cooling in a refrigerator reddish violet crystals separated. These were triturated with a little hot water, filtered and washed with alcohol. Found : Co, 11.8; N, 30.7; SO₄, 19.0%. Calc. for [Co(*dl*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂SO₄·H₂O : Co, 11.7; N, 30.5; SO₄, 19.0%.

l-Methioninato *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) sulphate :

l-Methionine and *cis*-diammine *bis*(biguanide) cobalt(III) base were reacted as described above and the solution was neutralised with H₂SO₄. The sparingly soluble sulphate salt was recrystallised from a large volume of hot water. Found : Co, 11.2; N, 29.3; SO₄, 18.7; H₂O, 3.5%. Calc. for [Co(*l*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂SO₄·H₂O : Co, 11.3; N, 29.5; SO₄, 18.4; H₂O, 3.4%.

Elemental analyses were done by following standard methods. Equivalent weight was determined with the aid of H⁺ form cationexchanger (IR-120) column⁸. Conductance was determined with a Philips Bridge at 0.001M. Spectra of aqueous solutions were run in 1 cm cell over the range 320-600 nm in a Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Molar conductance of [Co(*dl*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂·I₂·H₂O in water was found to be 211 ohms⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ being in the expected range of bi-univalent electrolytes⁴. Its equivalent weight (339) was close to the required value (340). The electronic spectrum⁵ of this complex was extremely close to those of [Co(*dl*- α -alan)(BigH₂)₂]₂²⁺, [Co(*dl*-valin)(BigH₂)₂]₂²⁺, [Co(*l*-leuc)(BigH₂)₂]₂²⁺ in respect of spectral profile, band positions and molar extinction coefficients :

	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} (ϵ_{max})	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g} (ϵ_{max})
[Co(<i>dl</i> -meth)(BigH ₂) ₂] ₂ ²⁺	20.41(165) (kK)	27.90(214) (kK)
[Co(<i>dl</i> - α -alan)(BigH ₂) ₂] ₂ ²⁺	20.41(155)	27.78(187)
[Co(<i>dl</i> -valin)(BigH ₂) ₂] ₂ ²⁺	20.62(161)	27.78(199)
[Co(<i>l</i> -leuc)(BigH ₂) ₂] ₂ ²⁺	20.41(144)	27.78(78)

The properties of [Co(*l*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂²⁺ are also comparable to those of [Co(*dl*-meth)(BigH₂)₂]₂²⁺. It is thus clear that the above mixed chelates have [CoN₆O] chromophore i.e. methionine functions as a bidentate NO donor. The sulphur end of methionine remains unattached to cobalt(III). In the mixed chelate [Co(cys)(en)₂]⁺ (cysH₂ = cysteine; en = ethylenediamine) the cysteinate ligand has been shown to be attached to cobalt(III) as an SN bidentate donor⁶. The ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition appears at a lower energy (16.7 kK).

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Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes of Acrylamide

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AMIDES and lactams have invoked lot of interest as ligands in recent years, since in addition to the carbonyl group, these molecules possess an amine group as a potential donor site. Further, these

complexes are being widely used in polymerization processes. With transition metal ions only compounds have been reported that contain oxygen co-ordinated amides and lactams. This aroused our interest to study a number of lactams and amides as ligand. In earlier communication, we have described¹⁻³ complexes of lactams, nicotinamide and dicyandiamide, with some divalent metal ions. Though a few complexes of acrylamide with metal salts containing non-coordinating anions have been reported⁴⁻⁵, these reports are controversial so far as the bonding site (donor atom) is concerned. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the complexes of acrylamide with some divalent metal ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Absolute ethanol solution of the divalent metal salts were reacted with ethanolic solution of acrylamide in 1:6 and 1:8 proportions. Resulting solutions were refluxed for one hour and kept standing for one or two days when compounds crystallized out. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum. The metal and halogen or thiocyanate were analysed by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of complexes using Toshiniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens by Gouy's method at room temperature. Infrared spectra were recorded from Perkin-Elmer-337 and Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were measured with M/100 (chloroform+amide) solution by Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical data are recorded in Table I.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported have the general composition MX_2L_2 where $X=Cl^-$, Br^- or SCN^- and $L=$ acrylamide except the two pink cobalt complexes which have the formula $CoBr_2L_4$ and $Co(SCN)_2L_4$. Other cobalt(II) complexes are deep blue in colour, nickel(II) complexes are green, copper(II) complexes are either green or yellow, manganese(II) complexes are light pink, zinc and cadmium complexes are white. All the compounds are soluble in acetone, in which medium the molar conductance values are in the range of 5-12 mhos cm^2 indicating non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment of blue cobalt(II) complexes indicate a tetrahedral configuration whereas the pink complexes have higher moments suggestive of a spin free octahedral configuration. Nickel(II), copper(II) and manganese(II) complexes have moments in the range of 2.9-3.0, 1.75-1.82 and 5.9-5.92 B.M. respectively.

Infrared spectra of acrylamide show bands at 3350, 3180, 1680, 1620 and 1440 cm^{-1} region assignable⁶ to $\nu_{as}(N-H)$, $\nu_s(N-H)$, $\nu(C=O)$ (amide-I), $\delta(NH_2)$ (amide-II) and $\nu(C-N)$ respectively. In the complexes the band positions due to $\nu(N-H)$ remain almost unaltered whereas $\nu(C=O)$ is observed ~ 1660 and $\nu(C-N) \sim 1460$ indicating that acrylamide is bonded to the metal ions through the carbonyl oxygen atom. This has been further substantiated by observation⁷ of $\nu(M-O) \sim 420-450$ cm^{-1} region in the far infrared spectra of complexes. In case of thiocyanato complexes $\nu(C\equiv N)$ is observed ~ 2100 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group on the basis of earlier observations⁸.

Visible electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes classify them into two distinct categories

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF ACRYLAMIDE (L) COMPLEXES

Compounds	M.P. (°C)	ΔM (mhos. cm^2)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%Metal		%Halogen or thiocyanate		Electronic spectra ν_{max} in k.k. (ϵ)	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
1. $CoCl_2L_2$	230	5.8	4.5	21.24	21.6	25.72	26.07	16.5(950), 8.2(200)	
2. $CoBr_2L_2$	Above	250	6.5	4.6	16.02	16.27	44.03	44.3	16.3(940), 8.3(200)
3. $CoBr_2L_4$		245	7.4	4.9	11.31	11.67	31.55	31.78	18.8(35), 8.2(20)
4. $Co(SCN)_2L_4$		212	8.2	5.0	12.65	12.83	25.64	25.32	18.9(33), 8.1(20)
5. $NiCl_2L_2$	Above	250	9.1	2.9	21.32	21.6	25.87	26.09	8.5(6), 13.3(6), 24.1(14)
6. $NiBr_2L_2$	Above	250	10.8	3.1	16.05	16.27	44.11	44.31	8.8(7), 13.5(7), 24.3(15)
7. $Ni(SCN)_2L_2$		237	11.5	3.0	18.14	18.51	36.24	36.62	9.1(7), 13.5(7), 24.5(14)
8. $CuCl_2L_2$	Above	250	8.4	1.8	22.74	22.97	25.26	25.64	14.8(35)
9. $CuBr_2L_2$	Above	250	6.8	1.82	17.03	17.38	43.38	43.72	15.1(38)
10. $Cu(SCN)_2L_2$	Above	250	7.5	1.75	19.51	19.74	35.91	36.07	17.8(42)
11. $MnCl_2L_2$		188	11.2	5.9	20.11	20.49	25.14	26.49	27.5(35), 24.6(2)
12. $MnBr_2L_2$		208	12.0	5.92	15.14	15.39	44.55	44.78	27.2(-3), 24.5(-2)
13. $ZnCl_2L_2$		112	8.2	—	23.01	23.48	25.03	25.47	
14. $Zn(SCN)_2L_2$		237	10.5	—	19.88	20.2	35.66	35.86	
15. $CdCl_2L_2$		165	8.8	—	34.28	34.52	21.58	21.81	
16. $CdBr_2L_2$		178	9.2	—	26.85	27.13	25.14	25.49	

COL₂X₂ type of complexes show two absorption bands ~16.5 (950) and ~8.5 (200) k.k. region attributable to ⁴A₂→⁴T_{1g} (P) and ⁴A₂→⁴T₁ (F) transitions respectively suggesting a tetrahedral stereochemistry of these complexes supported by their magnetic moment data. Complexes of the composition CoX₂L₄ also show two absorption bands ~18. (35) and 8.2 (20) k.k. region assignable to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}(F) transitions respectively. On the basis of the spectral bands and their magnetic moments a spin free octahedral configuration is indicated for these complexes supported by earlier observation⁹. All the nickel(II) complexes give rise to three absorption bands ~8.5-9.1 (6), 13.3-13.5 (6) and 24.1-24.5 (14) k.k. regions due to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F), ³T_{1g}(F) and ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively and a possible spin free octahedral stereochemistry is suggested¹⁰ for these complexes. Copper(II) halide complexes show one broad band ~14.8-15.1 (38) k.k. region and the thiocyanate complex shows one band at 17.8 (42) k.k. region. Presumably the halide complexes have a distorted octahedral configuration¹¹ whereas the thiocyanate complex is planar. Two bands are observed in case of manganese(II) complexes ~27.5 and 24.6 k.k. regions suggesting¹² an octahedral environment about the metal ion. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral studies zinc and cadmium complexes have a possible tetrahedral geometry.

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Unstable Chromium(III) Chlorate

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PERCHLORATES and chlorates are powerful oxidizing agents and the thermal decomposition of intimate mixtures of chromium(III) oxide and LiClO₄, TiClO₄, KClO₄ and KClO₃ resulted in the formation of metal dichromates. Chromium(III) perchlorate hexahydrate on thermolysis⁵ gives chromium(VI) oxide and chromyl chloride. In this context, it was thought interesting to study the thermal behaviour of chromium(III) chlorate and to identify the decomposition products in order to find out whether Cr(III) is oxidized into Cr(VI) by the chlorate moiety. No information is available in the literature about the preparation and existence of this compound. In this note is reported the attempted method of isolation of Cr(ClO₃)₃ and its immediate oxidation to Cr(VI).

Experimental

10 m moles (6.622 g) of Cr₂(SO₄)₃·15H₂O are dissolved in 100 ml water and to which is added a solution containing 30 m moles (9.667 g) of Ba(ClO₃)₂·H₂O in 100 ml water. The contents are stirred for 15 min and the precipitated BaSO₄ is filtered. The filtrate containing Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution is checked for Cr(III) content by iodometry after oxidizing Cr(III) with potassium peroxydisulphate⁶. A known amount of the Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution was taken in a petri dish and was evaporated on a water bath. Blue colour of the solution persisted till the complete evaporation of water and suddenly the thick liquid turned into a red mass. The electronic spectrum was recorded on a Carl Zeiss DMR 21 recording spectrometer and the infrared spectrum was taken on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrometer in nujol mull. The X-ray powder photograph was taken using CuK α radiation and Debye-Scherrer camera of diameter 11.46 cm.

Results and Discussion

The red mass obtained, is found to be hygroscopic and its electronic spectrum in water exhibited absorptions at 23.0, 28.8 and 39.0 kK, which are the characteristic of [CrO₅(OH)]⁻ species⁷. The infrared spectrum showed absorption bands at (cm⁻¹) 975s and 850w, b which are due⁸ to CrO₃. Further, the X-ray powder patterns of the solid showed the most intense lines at (Å) 4.23, 3.40 and 3.33 which correspond⁹ to CrO₃. Further confirmation of the solid was achieved by chemical analysis. Known amount of Cr(ClO₃)₃ solution was taken in an all-glass apparatus, with a provision to collect the liberated